

Evaluating the protective impact of *Mucuna pruriens* on lipid profile of albino rats exposed to potassium dichromate

¹R. O. Ideweale; ²B. J. Enagbonma; ²O. Osasumwen; ³E. E. Isemeye; ⁴B. A. Mudashiru; ¹C. E. Ilongwo and ⁵E. I. Ideweale

¹Department of Wood Materials Science, Forestry and Technology, University of Eastern Finland.

²Department of Environmental Management and Toxicology; Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, P.M.B. 1154, Benin City, Nigeria.

³Department of Environmental Health and Technology, University of Eastern Finland.

⁴Department of Chemistry, Ohio University.

⁵Narrow Way Clinic, Benin City, Nigeria.

Abstract

Lipid metabolism is essential for maintaining cellular energy balance and overall metabolic health. However, exposure to environmental pollutants such as potassium dichromate disrupts lipid homeostasis, contributing to dyslipidemia and increased cardiovascular risk. This study investigates the protective potential of *Mucuna pruriens*, a medicinal plant rich in bioactive compounds, against potassium dichromate-induced dyslipidemia in albino rats. Twenty male albino rats were divided into four groups: a control group (CN), 2 ml of potassium dichromate (Cr)-treated group, 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of *Mucuna pruriens* (Mp) treated groups and 0.75 ml of *Mucuna pruriens*-treated groups. Biochemical analyses were conducted on days 7 and 14 to evaluate total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), LDL/HDL ratio, and Coronary Risk Index (CRI). Results indicated that potassium dichromate exposure led to increased TC, LDL, and TG levels, along with a decrease in HDL. *Mucuna pruriens* supplementation demonstrated dose-related lipid-modulating effects, with the 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group showing significant improvements in HDL levels, LDL/HDL ratio, and CRI. The 0.75 ml of Mp exhibited a modest reduction in TC and LDL levels. These findings highlight *Mucuna pruriens* as a promising natural intervention for mitigating heavy metal-induced metabolic disruptions.

Keywords: Cardiovascular diseases, Lipid metabolism, Natural products, Rat model, Toxicology

*Corresponding Author: benjamin.enagbonma@uniben.edu

Introduction

Lipid metabolism is a critical physiological process that ensures energy homeostasis and cellular function (Xu and Huang 2020; Sese-Owei et al. 2020). However, disruptions in lipid balance can lead to metabolic disorders such as dyslipidemia (Natesan and Kim 2021). These disorders increase the risk of cardiovascular diseases, oxidative stress, and other systemic complications (Rotariu et al. 2022; Enagbonma et al. 2022a). Environmental pollutants, particularly heavy metals like potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$), have been implicated in lipid metabolism disturbances due to their toxic effects on cellular structures and biochemical pathways (Mohamed et al. 2021). Potassium dichromate is a hexavalent chromium compound that is widely used in industrial applications such as tanning, electroplating, and pigment production (Gerenfes et al. 2022; Lunk 2015). It is a known environmental contaminant with severe health implications (Wang et al. 2016). It also induces oxidative stress, alters lipid profiles, and contributes to organ damage, particularly in the liver and kidneys, which are essential for lipid metabolism (Mary Momo et al. 2019).

The toxic effects of potassium dichromate are largely attributed to its ability to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to lipid peroxidation, membrane damage, and dysregulation of lipid transport mechanisms (Navya et al. 2018). Exposure to potassium dichromate has been shown to increase low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels, decrease high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels, and alter total cholesterol and triglyceride levels, all of which are biomarkers of cardiovascular health (Feng et al. 2018). The imbalance in these lipid parameters contributes to an increased risk of atherosclerosis, hypertension, and other cardiovascular complications (Gaggini et al. 2022). Given the widespread exposure to potassium dichromate in occupational and environmental settings, it is essential to explore protective strategies that can mitigate its adverse effects on lipid metabolism.

One promising approach to counteract potassium dichromate-induced dyslipidemia is the use of natural antioxidants and phytochemicals with lipid-lowering properties (Mohsen et al. 2024;

Enagbonma et al. 2022b). *Mucuna pruriens*, commonly known as velvet bean, is a tropical leguminous plant widely recognized for its medicinal benefits (Pal et al. 2025). Traditionally used in Ayurveda and other herbal medicine systems, *Mucuna pruriens* is rich in bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, polyphenols, and L-DOPA (L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine), which contribute to its antioxidant, neuroprotective, and metabolic-modulating properties (Zahra et al. 2022). Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of *Mucuna pruriens* in reducing oxidative stress (Chandran et al. 2022), improving lipid profiles (Dimitry et al. 2023), and enhancing overall metabolic health (Jadhav et al. 2022). However, its role in protecting against heavy metal-induced dyslipidemia remains an area of interest requiring further investigation.

The ability of *Mucuna pruriens* to modulate lipid metabolism is attributed to its antioxidative and anti-inflammatory effects (Yadav et al. 2024). By scavenging ROS, reducing lipid peroxidation, and enhancing enzymatic antioxidant defenses, *Mucuna pruriens* may help restore lipid balance and protect against metabolic disturbances induced by potassium dichromate exposure (Boniface et al. 2024). Additionally, its impact on lipid-regulating enzymes, cholesterol transport mechanisms, and liver function suggests its potential as a natural therapeutic agent in managing dyslipidemia (Gu et al. 2023). Although, existing studies have explored its benefits in the general metabolic health (Rathi et al. 2002), the influence of *M. pruriens* on specific lipid parameters following exposure to potassium dichromate remains largely unexplored. This study aims to evaluate the protective impact of *Mucuna pruriens* on the lipid profile of albino rats exposed to potassium dichromate. By analyzing key lipid parameters, including LDL, HDL, total cholesterol, and triglyceride levels, this research seeks to determine whether *Mucuna pruriens* supplementation can mitigate the dyslipidemic effects of potassium dichromate. Understanding the extent to which *Mucuna pruriens* influences lipid homeostasis in a toxicological setting will contribute valuable knowledge to its potential application in preventing heavy metal-induced metabolic disorders. It is hypothesized that *Mucuna pruriens* supplementation will improve lipid profile parameters by reducing LDL and total cholesterol levels while increasing HDL levels in

albino rats exposed to potassium dichromate. This suggests that *Mucuna pruriens* may serve as a protective agent against potassium dichromate-induced dyslipidemia. To achieve the study's objectives, the following research questions will be addressed: (i) how does potassium dichromate exposure affect the lipid profile of albino rats? (ii) can *Mucuna pruriens* administration counteract dyslipidemia caused by potassium dichromate? (iii) does the duration of *Mucuna pruriens* administration influence its protective effects on lipid metabolism? By investigating *Mucuna pruriens*' role in lipid regulation under toxic conditions, this study will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on herbal medicine, phytotherapy, and environmental toxicology. Additionally, the findings may pave the way for further research into the clinical applications of *Mucuna pruriens* in lipid management and heavy metal detoxification.

Materials and methods

Experimental design

A total of 20 male albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*), weighing 142 g, were used for the experiment. The rats were randomly divided into four groups (n = 5 per group) and housed in standard laboratory conditions with a 12-hour light/dark cycle, at a temperature of 25 ± 2°C, and ad libitum access to food and water. The experimental duration was 14 days, with biochemical assessments conducted on day 7 and day 14.

Animal grouping and treatment

The animals were assigned to the following groups:

1. Control group (CN) – Received distilled water only.
2. 2 ml of potassium dichromate group - (2 ml of Cr).
3. 2 ml of potassium dichromate (Cr) + 0.5 ml of *Mucuna pruriens* (Mp) group - (2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp)
4. 0.75 ml of *Mucuna pruriens* (Mp) only group- (0.75 ml of Mp).

The doses of potassium dichromate and *Mucuna pruriens* were determined based on previous toxicological and pharmacological studies (Saikarthik et al. 2016; Gumbleton and Nicholls 1988). The treatments were administered via oral gavage once daily for 14 days.

Preparation of Mucuna pruriens extract

Mucuna pruriens leaves were obtained from Ekosodin a village at Ovia North Local Government Area of Edo State, authenticated at the Department of Botany, and air-dried at room temperature. The dried leaves were ground into powder and extracted using ethanol (70%) via cold maceration for 48 hours. The extract was filtered, concentrated using a rotary evaporator, and stored at 4°C until use.

Induction of toxicity with potassium dichromate

Potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) was dissolved in distilled water and administered orally at 2 mg/kg body weight (b.w.) to induce oxidative stress and lipid profile alterations.

Blood sample collection and lipid profile analysis

At the end of 7 and 14 days, the rats were anesthetized using ketamine (50 mg/kg b.w.) and euthanized. Blood samples were collected via cardiac puncture into plain tubes and centrifuged at 3,500 rpm for 10 minutes to obtain serum. The serum was stored at -20°C until biochemical analysis. The following lipid parameters were assessed using standard enzymatic colorimetric kits (Enagbonma et al. 2015): total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), LDL/HDL ratio, and coronary risk index (CRI) which were calculated by TC/HDL.

Statistical analysis

All data were analyzed using Past v4.03, and results were expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post-hoc test was used to determine statistical significance, with p < 0.05 considered significant.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted following the ethical guidelines for laboratory animal care and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC). All experimental procedures

were in accordance with the guidelines of the National Research Council (NRC) for the use of laboratory animals.

Results

Total cholesterol of albino rats across different experimental groups

The cholesterol levels (mg/dL) across different groups at 7 and 14 days are shown in Fig 1. The

control group (CN) shows minimal variation over time, while the 2ml of Cr and 0.75 ml of Mp groups exhibit a decrease in cholesterol levels at 14 days, suggesting a potential cholesterol-lowering effect. In contrast, the 2ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group shows a slight increase over time, indicating a possible cholesterol-elevating effect or resistance to reduction.

Fig. 1. Total cholesterol of albino rats across different experimental groups at two time points (7 days and 14 days).

Triglyceride levels of albino rats across different experimental groups

The triglyceride levels (mg/dL) across different experimental groups at two time points (7 days and 14 days) is shown in Fig 2. The control group (CN) maintains high triglyceride levels with minimal change over time. The 2 mL of Cr group shows the lowest triglyceride levels at 7 days, but there is a significant increase by 14 days, suggesting a time-dependent effect. The 2 ml of

Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group follows a similar pattern, with an initial reduction in triglyceride levels at 7 days but an increase at 14 days, though it remains lower than the control. The 0.75 ml of Mp group maintains consistently high triglyceride levels, similar to the control group, with little variation over time. Overall, most groups exhibit a rise in triglyceride levels over time, indicating a possible delayed metabolic response or reduced effectiveness of treatments beyond 7 days.

Fig. 2. Triglyceride levels of albino rats across different experimental groups at two time points (7 days and 14 days).

HDL levels of albino rats across different experimental groups

The HDL (good cholesterol) levels across different groups at 7 and 14 days are shown in Fig 3. The control (CN) group remains relatively stable with a slight decrease over time. The 2 mL of Cr group has lower HDL levels than the control, with a further decline at 14 days. The 2 ml of Cr + 0.5

ml of Mp group is the only group showing a significant increase in HDL over time, suggesting a beneficial effect of this combination. In contrast, the 0.75 ml of Mp group starts with high HDL levels at 7 days but experiences a sharp decline by 14 days. Overall, most groups show a decrease in HDL over time, except for the 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group, which appears to enhance HDL levels.

Fig. 3. HDL levels of albino rats across different experimental groups at two time points (7 days and 14 days).

LDL levels of albino rats across different experimental groups

LDL levels across different treatment groups over 7 and 14 days, revealing a general decrease over time (Fig. 4). The control (CN) group exhibits a slight reduction, while the 2 ml of Cr and 0.75 ml

of Mp groups show a more pronounced decline, with the latter displaying the most significant reduction. The 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group starts with the highest LDL levels and decreases slightly by day 14. These trends suggest potential LDL-lowering effects of the treatments, with 0.75 ml of Mp being the most effective.

Fig. 4. LDL levels of albino rats across different experimental groups at two time points (7 days and 14 days).

LDL/HDL levels of albino rats across different experimental groups

The LDL/HDL ratio across different treatment groups over 7 and 14 days. Generally, most groups show a slight reduction in LDL/HDL over time, except for the CN (control) group, which exhibits a slight increase (Fig. 5). The 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group initially has the highest

LDL/HDL ratio at 7 days but significantly decreases by 14 days, suggesting a potential improvement in lipid balance. The 2 ml of Cr and 0.75 ml of Mp groups remain relatively stable, showing only minor changes. These trends indicate that the 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp treatment may have a strong effect on lowering LDL/HDL, while other treatments maintain or slightly improve lipid balance over time.

Fig. 5. LDL/HDL levels of albino rats across different experimental groups at two time points (7 days and 14 days).

Coronary Risk Index levels of albino rats across different experimental groups

The Coronary Risk Index (CRI) across different treatment groups over 7 and 14 days (Fig. 6). The CN (control), 2ml of Cr, and 0.75 ml of Mp groups show a slight increase in CRI over time, suggesting a minor worsening of cardiovascular risk. The 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group starts

with the highest CRI at 7 days but significantly decreases by 14 days, indicating an improvement in lipid balance and potential reduction in cardiovascular risk. The 2ml of Cr group maintains the lowest CRI across both time points. These findings suggest that while some treatments may slightly increase CRI, the 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp treatment shows a notable improvement over time.

Fig. 6. Coronary Risk Index levels of albino rats across different experimental groups at two time points (7 days and 14 days).

Discussion

The present study investigated the impact of potassium dichromate exposure on lipid metabolism and the potential protective role of *Mucuna pruriens* supplementation in albino rats. The results revealed significant alterations in lipid profile parameters across different treatment groups. Exposure to potassium dichromate resulted in significant dysregulation of lipid parameters, as evidenced by increased total cholesterol (TC), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and triglyceride (TG) levels, along with a decrease in high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels. These findings are consistent with previous studies demonstrating that potassium dichromate induces oxidative stress, disrupts lipid transport mechanisms, and promotes lipid peroxidation (Enagbonma 2016). The elevated Coronary Risk Index (CRI) in this group highlights the potential long-term cardiovascular risks posed by chromium toxicity (Boluda et al. 2023).

The administration of *Mucuna pruriens* extract demonstrated **dose-related** effects on lipid metabolism. The *Mucuna pruriens* group (0.75 ml of Mp) showed a modest reduction in TC and LDL levels over time, suggesting a potential lipid-lowering effect. This aligns with existing literature indicating that *Mucuna pruriens* possesses hypolipidemic properties due to its rich flavonoid and polyphenolic content, which exert antioxidative and anti-inflammatory effects (Deli et al. 2020; Tavares et al. 2015). The group administered 0.75 ml of Mp exhibited a contrasting lipid profile pattern, which stands out from other treatment groups. This divergence is characterized by a reduction in total cholesterol and triglycerides but with elevated LDL-C levels. Such a profile may indicate complex lipid-modulating properties of the extract at this particular dose, possibly reflecting a threshold effect or a biphasic dose response (Deli et al. 2020; Tavares et al. 2015). The implications of this are significant, as elevated LDL-C levels are a known risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, despite the reduction in other lipid parameters (Enagbonma et al. 2015). Therefore, while the reduction in total cholesterol and triglycerides might appear beneficial, the increase in LDL-C demands caution. It may suggest that at 0.75 ml, Mp extract alters lipid metabolism in a way that potentially offsets any cardioprotective effects.

This warrants further investigation, particularly to elucidate the mechanistic basis for such dose-specific effects, which could be related to bioactive compounds acting differently at varying concentrations. Emphasizing this atypical response is crucial to prevent underestimation of the study's findings and may help stimulate further focused research.

Interestingly, the combined administration of Cr and *Mucuna pruriens* group (2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp) exhibited a biphasic response in lipid parameters. While HDL levels significantly increased over time, indicating a protective effect, TC and TG levels showed an initial reduction followed by a slight increase at 14 days. This suggests that *Mucuna pruriens* may have complex metabolic effects, potentially influencing lipid synthesis pathways or feedback regulatory mechanisms (Gramsbergen et al. 2011). Additionally, the LDL/HDL ratio and CRI were markedly reduced in the 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group by day 14, supporting the hypothesis that *Mucuna pruriens* supplementation can mitigate potassium dichromate-induced dyslipidemia and lower cardiovascular risk (Dev and Pathak 2021).

A key observation in this study was the time-dependent variation in lipid parameters. The Cr group displayed worsening lipid profiles from day 7 to day 14, indicating progressive metabolic disruption due to sustained oxidative stress. Conversely, the *Mucuna pruriens*-treated groups exhibited either stabilization or improvement in lipid profiles over time. This suggests that *Mucuna pruriens* exerts its protective effects through gradual modulation of lipid metabolism, possibly by enhancing antioxidant defense mechanisms and promoting lipid clearance pathways (Concessao et al. 2020).

The fluctuating TG levels in different groups further highlight the dynamic nature of lipid metabolism in response to toxic insults and therapeutic interventions. The observed initial reduction followed by an increase in TG levels in the 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp group may be due to adaptive metabolic responses, compensatory lipid synthesis, or variations in lipid mobilization over time (Gramsbergen et al. 2011).

The differential effects of *Mucuna pruriens* administration alone or in combination with Cr

underscore the importance of dose optimization for therapeutic applications. While both doses exhibited lipid-lowering effects, the 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp showed superior efficacy in increasing HDL levels and reducing the CRI and LDL/HDL ratio. The slight increase in TC and TG levels at day 14 in this group, suggests that prolonged high-dose administration may require careful monitoring to avoid potential metabolic imbalances.

The findings from this study align with previous research indicating that *Mucuna pruriens* can modulate lipid profiles through its bioactive compounds, which enhance lipid metabolism and reduce oxidative stress (Indira et al. 2023).

Nevertheless, this study is not without limitations. First, the sample size was relatively small, which might affect the generalizability of the findings. Second, the study did not assess long-term outcomes or histopathological changes in organs, which could provide more comprehensive safety data. Third, the absence of mechanistic assays such as enzyme activity measurements or gene expression analysis limits the ability to fully explain the observed lipid alterations. Lastly, we used a single species and sex of animal, which may not capture the full range of biological variability. Despite these limitations, the findings contribute valuable preliminary data suggesting both therapeutic potential and risks associated with Mp extract. Future studies with larger cohorts, extended duration, and detailed mechanistic explorations are warranted to validate and expand upon these results.

Conclusion

In summary, potassium dichromate exposure significantly disrupted lipid metabolism in albino rats, increasing TC, LDL, and TG levels while decreasing HDL levels. *Mucuna pruriens* supplementation demonstrated a **dose-related** protective effect, with the 2 ml of Cr + 0.5 ml of Mp treatment, showing the most pronounced improvements in lipid parameters and decline in coronary risk index (CRI) cardiovascular risk markers. These findings support the potential application of *Mucuna pruriens* as a natural therapeutic agent for managing heavy metal-induced dyslipidemia and warrant further research into its clinical relevance and

mechanisms of action as well as further studies are required to ascertain this claim.

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